

Electronic Supplementary Information

**A 2D graphene-manganese oxide nanosheet
hybrid synthesized by a single step
liquid-phase co-exfoliation method for
supercapacitor applications**

Beatriz Mendoza-Sánchez, João Coelho, Anuj Pokle and Valeria Nicolosi*

*To whom correspondence should be addressed: beatrix.mendoza@gmail.com

S1 Experimental section

Electrode manufacture. Electrodes of 1 cm² area were spray-deposited onto indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass substrates (7 Ω/ sq sheet resistance) using a spray deposition equipment (*USI Prism Ultracoat 300*). The spray-deposition method has been described elsewhere.^[1,2] Prior to spray-deposition of electrochemically active material, the substrates were pre-coated with a 5 nm layer of PEI (sprayed from a 0.1 % w/w aqueous solution). Briefly, suspensions of electrochemically active material were fed into an automated pumping system that delivered the suspension at the tip of a ultrasonic spray head at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. Ultrasonic vibrations desintegrated the fluid into small drops producing a mist that was propelled away from the spray forming tip by a low pressure air (69 kPa) stream in the form of a spray cone. The mist was then deposited onto substrates attached to a hot plate that maintained a temperature suitable for evaporation of the fugitive carrier liquid (isopropanol, 95 °). The spray head was moved at a constant spray height (35 mm) and speed (100 mm s⁻¹) by an automated gantry in *x* and *y* directions drawing a previously designed and specified spray pattern that produced a uniform film.

Equipment and characterization techniques. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained using a *FEI-Titan* operated at 300 keV; Helium Ion Microscopy (HIM) was performed in a *Zeiss Orion* microscope operated at an acceleration voltage of 30kV and current of 1.2pA. A charge neutralization system was applied using an electron flood gun; X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed in a fully automated *Bruker D5000* powder diffractometer equipped with a monochromatic Cu K α radiation source ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm) and a secondary monochromator. XRD patterns were collected between 10 ° < 2 θ < 80 °, with a step size of 2 θ = 0.05 ° and a count time of 12 s/step. The samples were supported on a monocrystalline silicon; Raman (RS) spectra were recorded at room temperature using a *Witec Alpha 300* system with a laser excitation wavelength of 532 nm. A laser power of ≈ 0.4 mW was used with a 20x objective lens. Spectra were acquired for each sample by averaging 10 distinct spectra, each with an acquisition time of 30s; Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) measurements were performed with a *Perkin Elmer Pyris 1* thermogravimetric analyzer in air at a flow rate of 20 ml min⁻¹ and heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ from room temperature to 900 °C. A mass of about 7 mg was used for each test; Surface area and porosity analysis was performed in a *Quantachrome Nova*

4200e surface area analyzer at 77.4 K. The surface area was determined by analyzing the nitrogen adsorption isotherms using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. All samples were outgassed in nitrogen atmosphere at 100 °C for 16 hours before measurements; Spray deposition was performed in a *USI Prism Ultracoat 300* spray deposition equipment; Ultrasonication was performed in a *Elmasonic P120H (Fisher FB11207)* sonic bath; Centrifugation was performed in a *Thermoscientific Heraeus Multifuge X1* centrifuge; Electrode thickness was determined by step height measurements in a *Dektak 6M* profilometer (*Veeco Instruments, Inc*) and the weight of deposited films was measured using a *Sartorius Ultramicrobalance MSE-2.7S-000-DF* with a 0.0001 mg readability; Electrochemical measurements were performed in a *Reference 600/EIS300 Gamry* potentiostat/galvanostat.

S2 Further TEM Analysis

Figure S1: (a) TEM image of the graphene-manganese oxide nanosheet hybrid and corresponding diffraction pattern of an underlying graphene flake taken at the area marked with a red circle.

The diffraction pattern shows the typical hexagonal sixfold symmetry of graphene.^[3, 4]

S3 Profile matching analysis of MOFN, MON and PEMO

Figure S2: Profile matching analysis of (a) MOFN, (b) MON and (c) PEMO.

S4 Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of MOFN, MON, graphene and GMOH was performed. The as acquired TGA curves as well as the TGA derivative curves are shown in Figure S3. All samples evidenced a first stage of weight loss between 25 °C and 230 °C; this was attributed mainly to the removal of solvent and water. The loss of the PEG-PPG-PEG copolymer is known to occur between 190 °C and 350 °C.^[5-7] It is likely that the weight losses registered at 223 °C (for MOFN) and 230 °C (for MON)(evident in the TGA derivatives shown in Figures S3a and S3b respectively) correspond to the degradation of PEG-PPG-PEG copolymer residual from the synthesis. The TGA derivative curves for MOFN, MON and GMOH showed weight losses at 548 °C, 552 °C, and 519 °C respectively. These can be attributed to the removal of remaining adsorbed water as well as the removal of oxygen from the MnO_2 lattice inducing a transformation to Mn_2O_3 .^[8,9] The graphene TGA curve and its derivative (Figure S3c) showed

that graphene gets degraded at 704 °C. This graphene degradation peak was moved to a lower temperature of 446 °C in the case of GMOH. This is known to be due to a catalytic effect of manganese oxides.^[10] The TGA curve of GMOH shown in Figure S3c shows weight losses of 18.5 %, 15.5 %, and 1.75 % attributed to water evaporation, graphene degradation, and oxygen removal, respectively. On these basis, the ratio of graphene/manganese oxide in GMOH was calculated as 19 %/ 81 %.

Figure S3: Thermogravimetric analysis curves and corresponding derivatives for (a) MOFN, (b) MON, (c) graphene, and (d) GMOH.

S5 Nitrogen adsorption isotherms

Figure S4: BET nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms for (a) MOFN, (b) MON, and (c) GMOH. The labels describe the multipoint BET surface area.

S6 Equations for calculations of energy and power of symmetric supercapacitors

Capacitance C was calculated from galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments according to the following equation:

$$C = \frac{I\Delta t}{\Delta V} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where I is the current (A), Δt (s) is the discharge time, and $\Delta V = V_2 - V_1$ where V_2 (V) is the potential at the beginning of discharge, after the IR potential drop, and V_1 (V) is the potential at the end of discharge.

The capacitances per unit volume and mass were calculated using Equation S1 divided by $B_1 = \text{volume (cm}^3\text{) or mass (g)}$ of the two electrodes in the symmetric device

Energy and power per unit volume were calculated as follows:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \frac{C\Delta V^2}{3600B_2} \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$P = \frac{E}{\Delta t B_2} \quad (\text{S3})$$

where C , ΔV , Δt are defined as above, $B_2 = \text{volume (cm}^3\text{) or mass (kg)}$ of the two electrodes in the symmetric device, and 3600 is a conversion factor from Ws to Wh.

S7 Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies of the thick MON, GMOH and PEMO electrodes were performed and the EIS data is shown in Figure S5. The results are discussed in the main text.

Figure S5: EIS data plots for thick electrodes of MON, GMOH and PEMO: (a) Nyquist plot at the 1 mHz to 2 MHz frequency region, (b) close-up of Nyquist plot at the high frequency region, (c) and (d) Bode plot. (e) capacitance as function of frequency.

The EIS data were fitted to the equivalent electrical circuits (EECs) shown in Figure S6.

The construction of models was guided by references^[11–13]

The EEC elements are defined as follows :

Model 1

- $R1$ is the sum of the ohmic resistances of the electrolyte, electrical contacts, current collector, and electrode.

Figure S6: Equivalent electrical circuits used to fit EIS data.

- $CPE1$ is a constant phase element representing the capacitance of a inhomogeneous film at the current collector-electrode interface (high frequency).
- $R2$ is the charge transfer resistance at the current collector-electrode interface (at high frequency).
- $CPE2$ is a constant phase element representing the capacitance (double layer plus pseudocapacitive contributions) of a inhomogeneous electrode (at medium-low frequency).

Model 2

- $R1$ is the sum of the ohmic resistances of the electrolyte, electrical contacts, current collector, and electrode.
- $CPE1$ is a constant phase element representing the capacitance of a inhomogeneous electrode (at all frequency range)
- $R2$ is the charge transfer resistance of the electrode (at all frequency range).
- $Wo1$ is the generalized finite length Warburg impedance element of the open circuit-type (terminates in a infinite impedance and is also described as plane-restricted) and was used to describe a distributed diffusion impedance within the electrode.

The impedance of a constant phase element Z_{CPE} is defined as,^[12]

$$Z_{CPE} = \frac{1}{T_{CPE}(i\omega)^{\alpha_{CPE}}} \quad (S4)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, ω is the angular frequency, T_{CPE} is the capacitance when $\alpha_{CPE} = 1$, and α_{CPE} is the constant phase exponent ($0 \leq \alpha_{CPE} \leq 1$). A CPE element was used instead of a capacitor to account for inhomogeneities of the film.^[12]

The impedance of the generalized finite length Warburg impedance element Z_{W_o} is defined as,^[12]

$$Z_{W_o} = \frac{R \coth[(iT\omega)^P]}{(iT\omega)^P} \quad (\text{S5})$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, ω is the angular frequency, R (Ω) is the limiting diffusion resistance, $T = L^2/D$ (s) where L is the effective diffusion length (cm) and D ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) is the effective diffusion coefficient, and P is an exponent between 0 and 1.

Tables S1 and S2 summarize the values of the EECs obtained by fitting to the EIS data.

Table S1: Parameters obtained by fitting the model 1 to the EIS data of the GMOH electrode.

Electrode	GMOH
Thickness (nm)	2936.4
R_1 (Ω)	13.7
$\text{CPE}_1\text{-T}$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{s}^\alpha$)	5.7E-5
$\text{CPE}_1\text{-}\alpha$	0.82
R_2 (Ω)	4.2
$\text{CPE}_2\text{-T}$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{s}^\alpha$)	14E-3
$\text{CPE}_2\text{-}\alpha$	0.85
χ^2	8E-3
Frequency range (Hz)	1E-2 to 200E+03

Table S2: Parameters obtained by fitting the model 2 to the EIS data of MON and PEMO electrodes.

Electrode	MON	PEMO
Thickness (nm)	2804.9	3136.5
R_1 (Ω)	15.0	13.3
$\text{CPE}_1\text{-T}$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{s}^\alpha$)	3.8E-5	4.0E-05
$\text{CPE}_1\text{-}\alpha$	0.88	0.88
R_2 (Ω)	95.0	118.4
$W_{o1}\text{-R}$ (Ω)	2.7E-4	1.4E-4
$W_{o1}\text{-T}$ (s)	6.1E-19	5.0E-20
$W_{o1}\text{-P}$	0.17	0.17
χ^2	4.2E-3	1.9E-3
Frequency range (Hz)	1E-1 to 200E+03	1E-1 to 200E+03

The real capacitance C_R was calculated using the following equation:^[13]

$$C_R = \frac{-Z_i}{2\pi f |Z|^2} \quad (\text{S6})$$

where Z_i is the imaginary component of the impedance Z , and f is frequency.

Table S3: Capacitance from EIS data using Equation S6. In brackets, the values predicted according to Figure 4 in the main text.

Electrode	MON	GMOH	PEMO
Thickness (nm)	2804.9	2936.4	3136.5
C_R/area (mF cm ⁻²)	8.6 (18)	26.6 (30)	16.8 (27)
C_R/volume (F cm ⁻³)	30.7 (64)	90.6 (100)	53.4 (80)

S8 Comparison of the performance of the GMOH versus other devices/electrodes previously reported

Table S4: Comparative table of the gravimetric capacitance of GMOH electrodes/symmetric supercapacitor versus other manganese oxide-based electrodes/devices. The letters “y” and “n” denote the presence and absence of polymeric binders, respectively.

Electrode or device	Thickness	Mass	Capacitance per			Electrolyte
			area	volume	mass	
GMOH electrode (n)	9701 nm	≈ 0.7118 mg cm ⁻²	80 mF cm ⁻² CV@5 mVs ⁻¹	82.5 F cm ⁻³ CV@5 mVs ⁻¹		0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
	69 nm	≈ 0.0149 mg cm ⁻²	2 mF cm ⁻² CV@5 mV s ⁻¹	300 F cm ⁻³ CV@5 mV s ⁻¹		0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
	304 nm	≈ 0.0784 mg cm ⁻²			217 F g ⁻¹ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
GMOH-GMOH supercapacitor (n)	430 nm	≈ 0.0509 mg		40.9 F cm ⁻³ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	73.5 F g ⁻¹ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (full cell)
MnO ₂ nanosheets mixed with GOG ^[10] (y)		2 mg			188 F g ⁻¹ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
Electrodeposited MnO ₂ onto GOG ^[14] (n)		0.2-0.5 mg cm ⁻²			348 F g ⁻¹ @1 mA g ⁻¹	1 M KCl (full cell asymmetric)
MnO ₂ needle-like deposited onto GO ^[15] (y)		5.6-15.2 mg			197 F g ⁻¹ @0.2 A g ⁻¹	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
MnO ₂ nanoparticles embedded in a-MEGO ^[16] (y)		0.7-1.4 mg			175 F g ⁻¹ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ (full cell asymmetric)
			630 F cm ⁻³ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	256 F g ⁻¹ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (full cell asymmetric)	

Table S5: Comparative table of the capacitance per unit volume and per unit area of GMOH electrodes/symmetric supercapacitor versus other electrodes/devices proposed for micro-supercapacitor applications. The letters “y” and “n” denote the presence and absence of polymeric binders, respectively. The abbreviation “IM” indicates inter-digitated micro-supercapacitor.

Electrode or device	Thickness	Mass	Capacitance per			Electrolyte
			area	volume	mass	
GMOH (this work) (n)	9701 nm	≈ 0.7118 mg cm ⁻²	80 mF cm ⁻² CV@5 mVs ⁻¹	82.5 F cm ⁻³ CV@5 mVs ⁻¹		0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
	69 nm	≈ 0.0149 mg cm ⁻²	2 mF cm ⁻² CV@5 mV s ⁻¹	300 F cm ⁻³ CV@5 mV s ⁻¹		0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
	304 nm	≈ 0.0784 mg cm ⁻²			217 F g ⁻¹ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
GMOH-GMOH supercapacitor (n)	430 nm	≈ 0.0509 mg		40.9 F cm ⁻³ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	73.5 F g ⁻¹ @0.25 A g ⁻¹	0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (full cell)
Activated graphene ^[17] (y)	40-50 μ m	1.59-2.54 mg cm ⁻²		60 F cm ⁻³		BMIMBF ₄ (full cell sym.)
MWCNTs LBL electrodes ^[18] (n)	250 nm			132 F cm ⁻³ CV@50 mV s ⁻¹		1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
Carbon onions ^[19] (n)	7 μ m			1.5 F cm ⁻³		1 M Et ₄ NBF ₄ /PC (full cell sym.)
Carbide derived carbons ^[20] (n)	2-120 μ m			80-180 F cm ⁻³		1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
Titanium carbide Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x ^[21] (n)	2-20 μ m	2-3 mg cm ⁻²		340 F cm ⁻³ @1 A g ⁻¹		1 M KOH (half cell)
	(y)	75-100 μ m	7-9 mg cm ⁻²		80 F g ⁻¹ CV@2 mV s ⁻¹	0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ (half cell)
Electrodeposited MnO ₂ ^[22] (n)			56.3 mF cm ⁻² @ 27.2 μ A cm ⁻²			1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ (IM)
PANI nanowires ^[23] (n)	400 nm			588 F cm ⁻³ @ 0.1 mA cm ⁻²		PVA-H ₂ SO ₄ (IM)
VN-NiO ^[24] (n)	650 nm		1.24 mF cm ⁻² @ 2.7 mA cm ⁻²	26.5 F cm ⁻³		1 M KOH (full cell asym.)
VS ₂ ^[25] (n)	150 nm		4.76 mF cm ⁻²	317 F cm ⁻³		PVA-BIMBF ₄ (IM)
MoS ₂ ^[26] (n)	450 nm		8 mF cm ⁻²	178 F cm ⁻³		Aqueous (IM)

Table S6: Comparative table of energy and power performance per unit area and per unit volume of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor versus other electrodes/devices proposed for micro-supercapacitor applications. The letters “y” and “n” denote the presence and absence of polymeric binders, respectively. The abbreviation “IM” indicates inter-digitated micro-supercapacitor.

Electrode or device	Thickness	Mass	Energy/ area $\mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$	Power/ area mW cm^{-2}	Energy/ volume mWh cm^{-3}	Power/ volume W cm^{-3}
GMOH-GMOH supercapacitor (n)	430 nm	≈ 0.0509 mg			5.5 to 2.2	0.034 to 2.2
Carbon onions ^[19] 1 M Et ₄ NBF ₄ /PC,(n) (full cell sym.)	7 μm				1.5 to 0.5	32-250
Titanium carbide Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x ^[21] 1 M KOH, (n) (half cell)	2-20 μm	2-3 mg cm^{-2}			18.5 to 11.5	0.24-7.56
Titanium carbide Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x ^[21] 0.5 M K ₂ SO ₄ , (n) (full cell sym.)	75-100 μm	7-9 mg cm^{-2}			1 to 0.3	0.01 to 0.18
Electrodeposited MnO ₂ ^[22] 1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ , (n), (IM)			5.01E+3	12.02		
PANI nanowires ^[23] PVA-H ₂ SO ₄ ,(n) (IM)	400 nm				82	25
VN-NiO ^[24] 1 M KOH,(n) (full cell asym.)	650 nm		1	0.6		
CNT-Co(OH) ₂ ^[27] 1 M KOH,(n) (IM)			1.97	7.9		
Thin film ^[19] battery					8.5 to 0.4	1.5E-3 to 5.5E-3
25 mF supercapacitor ^[19]					0.3 to 0.1	0.6 to 10

Table S7: Comparative table of energy and power performance per unit mass of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor versus other manganese oxide-based symmetric supercapacitors and microsupercapacitors. The letters “y” and “n” denote the presence and absence of polymeric binders, respectively. The abbreviation “IM” indicates inter-digitated micro-supercapacitor.

Electrode or device	Thickness (nm)	Mass (mg)	Energy per mass Wh kg ⁻¹	Power per mass W kg ⁻¹
GMOH-GMOH supercapacitor (n)	430	≈ 0.0509	9.9 to 2.5	60.5 to 2506.3
MnO ₂ -CNT ^[28] 0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ , (n), (IM)	-	-	5.7	1160.0
MnO ₂ ^[29] 2 M KNO ₃ , (y), (full cell sym.)	-	-	1.9	3800
MnO ₂ ^[30] 0.1 M K ₂ SO ₄ , (y), (full cell sym.)	-	-	3.3	3080
Graphene/MnO ₂ ^[31] 1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ , (y), (full cell sym.)	-	-	8.0 to 1.5	8 to 2400
Graphene/MnO ₂ NW ^[32] 1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ , (y), (full cell sym.)	-	-	5.1 to 2.8	100 to 2500

References

- [1] B. Mendoza-Sanchez and P. S. Grant, B. Mendoza-Sanchez presented in part at the Fourth European Symposium on Super Capacitors and Applications, Bordeaux, France, 2010.
- [2] X. Zhao, B. T. T. Chu, B. Ballesteros, W. L. Wang, C. Johnston, J. M. Sykes and P. Grant, *Nanotechnology*, 2009, **20**, 065605.
- [3] Y. Hernandez, V. Nicolosi, M. Lotya, F. M. Blighe, Z. Sun, S. De, I. T. McGovern, B. Holland, M. Byrne, Y. K. Gun'Ko, J. J. Boland, P. Niraj, G. Duesberg, S. Krishnamurthy, R. Goodhue, J. Hutchison, V. Scardaci, A. C. Ferrari and J. N. Coleman, *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, 2008, **3**, 563.
- [4] B. Mendoza-Sanchez, B. Rasche, V. Nicolosi and P. Grant, *Carbon*, 2012, **52**, 337.
- [5] H. Kang, Y. Zhu, J. Shen, X. Yang, C. Chen, H. Cao and C. Li, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2010, **45**, 830.
- [6] L. Pei, K.-i. Kurumada, M. Tanigaki, M. Hiro and K. Susa, *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.*, 2005, **284**, 222.
- [7] Y. Zhao, H. Wang, X. Lu, X. Li, Y. Yang and C. Wang, *Mater. Lett.*, 2008, **62**, 143.
- [8] M. Puerta and P. Valerga, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1990, **67**, 344.
- [9] Y. Munaiah, B. G. Sundara Raj, T. Prem Kumar and P. Ragupathy, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2013, **1**, 4300.
- [10] J. Zhang, J. Jiang and X. S. Zhao, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2011, **115**, 6448.
- [11] X. Ren and P. G. Pickup, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1997, **420**, 251–257.
- [12] W. Sugimoto, H. Iwata, K. Yokoshima, Y. Murakami and Y. Takasu, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2005, **109**, 7330.
- [13] P. L. Taberna, P. Simon and J. F. Fauvarque, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2003, **150**, A292–A300.
- [14] Q. Cheng, J. Tang, J. Ma, H. Zhang, N. Shinya and L.-C. Qin, *Carbon*, 2011, **49**, 2917.
- [15] S. Chen, J. Zhu, S. Wu, Q. Han and X. Wang, *ACS Nano*, 2010, **4**, 2822.

- [16] X. Zhao, L. Zhang, S. Murali, M. D. Stoller, Q. Zhang, Y. Zhu and R. S. Ruoff, *ACS Nano*, 2012, **6**, 5404.
- [17] Y. Zhu, S. Murali, M. D. Stoller, K. J. Ganesh, W. Cai, P. J. Ferreira, A. Pirkle, R. M. Wallace, K. A. Cychoz, M. Thommes, D. Su, E. A. Stach and R. S. Ruoff, *Science*, 2011, **332**, 1537.
- [18] S. W. Lee, B.-S. Kim, S. Chen, Y. Shao-Horn and P. T. Hammond, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **131**, 671.
- [19] D. Pech, M. Brunet, H. Durou, P. Huang, V. Mochalin, Y. Gogotsi, P.-L. Taberna and P. Simon, *Nat. Nano.*, 2010, **5**, 651.
- [20] J. Chmiola, C. Largeot, P.-L. Taberna, P. Simon and Y. Gogotsi, *Science*, 2010, **328**, 480.
- [21] M. R. Lukatskaya, O. Mashtalir, C. E. Ren, Y. DallAgnese, P. Rozier, P. L. Taberna, M. Naguib, P. Simon, M. W. Barsoum and Y. Gogotsi, *Science*, 2013, **341**, 1502.
- [22] X. Wang, B. D. Myers, J. Yan, G. Shekhawat, V. Dravid and P. S. Lee, *Nanoscale*, 2013, **5**, 4119.
- [23] K. Wang, W. Zou, B. Quan, A. Yu, H. Wu, P. Jiang and Z. Wei, *Advanced Energy Materials*, 2011, **1**, 1068.
- [24] E. Eustache, R. Frappier, R. L. Porto, S. Bouhtiyia, J.-F. Pierson and T. Brousse, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2013, **28**, 104.
- [25] J. Feng, X. Sun, C. Wu, L. Peng, C. Lin, S. Hu, J. Yang and Y. Xie, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 17832.
- [26] L. Cao, S. Yang, W. Gao, Z. Liu, Y. Gong, L. Ma, G. Shi, S. Lei, Y. Zhang, S. Zhang, R. Vajtai and P. M. Ajayan, *Small*, 2013, **9**, 2905.
- [27] C.-H. Chen, D.-S. Tsai, W.-H. Chung, K.-Y. Lee, Y.-M. Chen and Y.-S. Huang, *J. Power Sources*, 2012, **205**, 510.
- [28] C.-C. Liu, D.-S. Tsai, W.-H. Chung, K.-W. Li, K.-Y. Lee and Y.-S. Huang, *J. Power Sources*, 2011, **196**, 5761.

- [29] V. Khomenko, E. Raymundo-Piñero and F. Béguin, *J. Power Sources*, 2006, **153**, 183.
- [30] T. Cottineau, M. Toupin, T. Delahaye, T. Brousse and D. Bélanger, *Appl. Phys. A*, 2006, **82**, 599.
- [31] Z. Fan, J. Yan, T. Wei, L. Zhi, G. Ning, T. Li and F. Wei, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2011, **21**, 2366.
- [32] Z.-S. Wu, W. Ren, D.-W. Wang, F. Li, B. Liu and H.-M. Cheng, *ACS Nano*, 2010, **4**, 5835.